

Front-line demonstration performance of salt-tolerant rice varieties in coastal saline soils

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A front-line demonstration (FLD) is one of the approaches used to discriminate technology generated through research. This unique program directly involves scientists, enabling them to have first-hand information. Considering the demand for salt-tolerant rice varieties in the coastal saline soils (Khar land) of Maharashtra, an FLD was launched by the Khar Land Research Station in nearby villages from 1997 to 1999.

Of the 8.6 million ha of salt-affected soils in India, 65,465 ha are covered by coastal saline soils in Maharashtra (GOM 1990). Farmers in this region generally grow conventional rice varieties using suboptimal input levels. Because they lack knowledge of rice production technology, their farms are not productive. The Khar Land Research Station, Panvel, has released improved, salt-tolerant rice varieties Panvel 1, Panvel 2, and Panvel 3 (Ingale et al 1993, Sawardekar et al 2000). However, the spread of these varieties has been limited because of weak extension activities and poor information dissemination programs. Moreover, the area devoted to seed production of these varieties at the research sta-

tion is limited. With financial and technical assistance of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi, an FLD of salt-tolerant improved rice varieties was conducted in farmers' fields. Cultivated were the salt-tolerant varieties listed in Table 1.

The farmer participants came from Koproli, Chirner, and Jui villages of Uran Tahasil District, Raigad. The experiment, conducted in 1997-99 kharif, aimed to study the technology gap, extension gap, technology index, and economics of rice production. Each demonstration farm was 0.20 ha. Soil types were clay loam, with low to medium N, and high to very high available P and K (Table 2). Salinity levels were from 6.3 to 9.3 dS m⁻¹. Rainfall distribution was uniform throughout the crop-growing period.

Production and economic data, as well as data on local practices, were collected.

The technology gap, extension gap, and technology index were calculated using the following formulas (Samui et al 2000):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Technology gap} &= \text{potential yield} \\ &\quad - \text{demonstration yield} \\ \text{Extension gap} &= \text{demonstration} \\ &\quad \text{yield} - \text{farmers' yield} \\ \text{Technology index} &= \text{potential} \\ &\quad \text{yield} - \text{demonstration} \\ &\quad \text{yield/potential yield} \\ &\quad \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

A comparison of productivity levels, yield gaps, technology gaps, and extension gaps between improved salt-tolerant rice varieties and local checks is shown in Table 1. Variety Panvel 1 recorded the highest rice yield (4.4 t ha⁻¹) in the 1998 kharif season. The results indicate the good impact of FLD trials on farming communities with coastal saline soils. Farmers were motivated by agrotechnologies applied in the

Table 2. Characteristics of soil in demonstration blocks (av data).

Soil parameter	Koproli	Chirner	Jui
pH	6.5	6.7	6.5
EC (dS m ⁻¹)	6.3	7.1	9.3
Organic C (%)	0.48	0.49	0.47
Available P ₂ O ₅ (kg ha ⁻¹)	68	72	71
Available K ₂ O (kg ha ⁻¹)	1,300	1,200	1,500

Table 1. Yield, technology gap, extension gap, and technology index of improved salt-tolerant rice varieties.

Year	Variety	Demonstrations (no.)	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			% increase over local check	Technology gap (kg ha ⁻¹)	Extension gap (kg ha ⁻¹)	Technology index (%)
			Potential	Demonstrations	Local check				
1997	CSR10	15	4,500	4,020	3,515	14.37	480	505	10.66
1998	Panvel 1	20	4,500	4,429	3,520	25.82	71	909	1.57
1999	Panvel 1	20	4,500	4,247	3,023	40.48	253	1,224	5.62

FLD trials and they adopted these in the succeeding years, resulting in enhanced productivity. The yield of rice, however, varied because of climate changes during the experimental period and the use of different varieties.

The observed technology gap may be attributed to dissimilarities in soil fertility, salinity, and weather conditions. Hence, a location-specific recommendation appears to be necessary to close the gap. The wide extension gap emphasizes the need to educate farmers. The technology index reflects the feasibility of using the evolved technology in farmers' fields. The lower the value of the

technology index, the more feasible the use of the technology is. The highest technology index, noted in 1997 kharif with variety CSR10, clearly indicates the existence of a wide gap between technologies developed at research stations and those used in farmers' fields.

Additional costs, mainly for inputs, were noted in the FLD trials, thus increasing the cost of cultivation over that of the local check. But gross returns and net returns were still substantial in the FLD trials. Higher benefit-cost ratios were seen with improved varieties than with local checks (Table 3).

References

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Table 3. Economics of rice cultivation.

Year	Variety	Cost of cultivation (Rs ha ⁻¹)				Gross return (Rs ha ⁻¹)		Net return (Rs ha ⁻¹)			Benefit-cost ratio	
		Input cost for demonstration (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Demonstration	Local check	Additional cost of cultivation in demonstration (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Demonstration	Local check	Demonstration	Local check	Additional return (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Demonstration	Local check
1997	CSR10	2,372	9,768	8,525	1,243	17,300	13,115	7,532	4,590	2,942	0.77	0.53
1998	Parvel 1	2,372	8,883	7,900	983	18,800	14,400	9,917	6,500	3,417	1.11	0.82
1999	Parvel 1	2,372	12,166	10,900	1,266	20,900	17,200	8,699	6,300	2,309	0.71	0.57

Extent of women's involvement in Indian rice cultivation

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As in other countries, nearly half of the available human resources in India are women. In traditional village communities, women are primarily involved in all stages of crop cultivation, from field preparation to harvesting of grains. In rural areas of India, most female workers help the men in farm operations, especially in the agricultural sector (Sherwani 1983). In general, women provide 60–70% of labor input. For rice, this pro-

portion reaches 80%. Gautam and Meenakshi (1992) indicated that the proportion of women in the agricultural labor force was more and their contribution to agriculture was greater than men's.

In 2000, we conducted a study at the Regional Research Station, Paiyur, to find out the extent of women farmers' involvement in rice cultivation. The data were collected at Palacode and Krishnagiri taluks of Dharmapuri

District in Tamil Nadu, India. Agriculture is the source of livelihood of the people in this area, with a wide variety of crops grown—cereals, millet, pulses, oilseeds, tomato, and mango. In this district, rice is grown on about 57,000 ha of land during the wet (Jul–Nov) and dry seasons (Dec–Mar). Canal and well-irrigation systems are fairly common.

One hundred and twenty women farmers were selected